

Trace Determination of Carbaryl (Sevin) in Field Water, Grapes, Vegetables and Blood Samples

VIKITA AGRAWAL and V. K. GUPTA*

Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University, Raipur-492 010

Manuscript received 10 May 1991, revised 26 May 1992, accepted 18 June 1992

A sensitive and selective spectrophotometric method for the determination of residues of carbaryl in field water, grapes, vegetables and blood sample is described. The method is based on the diazotisation of *p*-aminobenzoic acid with sodium nitrite/hydrochloric acid and coupling it with 1-naphthol obtained from hydrolysis of carbaryl in alkaline medium. The dye could be extracted into isoamyl alcohol and has stability of 24 h. Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.1–0.8 ppm.

Carbaryl (or sevin or 7744) is used on a large scale against broad spectrum of insects in field crops, fruits and vegetables. The maximum allowable concentration reported¹ at the work site is 5 mg m^{-3} (0.5 ppm). A survey of literature reveals several methods²⁻⁴ based on different techniques for its determination and most of which require hydrolysis prior to analysis.

Due to its toxicity and wide applicability, a simple, sensitive and selective method for the determination of carbaryl has been proposed here. The method is based on the diazotisation of *p*-aminobenzoic acid with sodium nitrite/hydrochloric acid and coupling it with 1-naphthol obtained from hydrolysis of carbaryl in alkaline medium. The dye obtained is then extracted into isoamyl alcohol. The extract has absorbance maxima at 470 nm and obeys Beer's law in the range 0.1–0.8 ppm. The method has been successfully applied for the determination of carbaryl in field water, vegetables, grapes, and blood samples. The method is found to be free from the interferences of various insecticides. The method is also compared with the other reported colorimetric methods and other analytical parameters have been optimised.

Results and Discussion

Beer's law was obeyed in the range 1–8 ppm in aqueous medium and 0.1–0.8 ppm in isoamyl alcohol extract. The pink coloured species formed by carbaryl has an absorbance maxima at 520 nm in aqueous sodium and after extraction, the absorbance maxima is 470 nm. Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were $20.06 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.010 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively in aqueous medium.

Effect of reagent concentration: 0.3 ml of PABA, 0.7 ml of sodium nitrite and 1 ml of 4 M sodium hydroxide were required for full colour development.

Effect of temperature: Temperature ranging from 15 to 40° did not cause any adverse effect on the colour of the dye. Temperature above 50° and below 15° resulted in low absorbance values.

Effect of foreign species: The tolerance limits (in ppm) of various foreign species (that caused $\pm 2\%$ error) associated with 40 μg of carbaryl/10 ml are as follows: parathion, malathion and paraquat (500 each), kethane (185), propoxur and 1-naphthol (150 each), Sb^{III} (750), Pb^{II} (300), Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} (50 each), sulphate (700), phosphate (450) and chloride (25). If 1-naphthol is present as contaminant or formed by decomposition of carbaryl it gives yellow colour, when the solution is rendered alkaline under normal conditions separation of 1-naphthol from the compound is not required as eight-fold excess of this has no appreciable effect on the determination. But if amounts higher than this is suspected, then the chloroform is to be washed twice 0.2–0.4 M sodium hydroxide solution and then with water to remove 1-naphthol before the chloroform is evaporated off and then the colour is developed.

The results of analysis of carbaryl in different samples are given in Table 1. Comparison of this method with other spectrophotometric methods is made in Table 2.

The proposed method is simple as it does not require elaborate clean up and preliminary hydrolysis. The method is selective as it is free from interference of propoxur and other pesticides. It can be successfully applied for the determination of carbaryl in field samples.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss spekol spectrophotometer was used for all spectral measurements.

Analytical reagent grade chemicals were used where available. Standard carbaryl (Northern Minerals Limited, India) stock solution of 1 mg ml^{-1} in ethanol, *p*-aminobenzoic acid (PABA) 0.5% (w/v) solution in ethanol and a 1 mg ml^{-1} aqueous sodium nitrite solution were used.

Preparation of calibration curve: To an aqueous solution (100 ml) containing 10–80 μg of carbaryl was added PABA reagent (0.3 ml) and the acidity was adjusted to $\sim 0.5 \text{ M}$ with HCl. After 2 min,

TABLE 1—RECOVERY OF CARBARYL IN DIFFERENT SAMPLES*

Sample	Solvent used	Carbaryl originally found μg	Carbaryl added μg	Total carbaryl found μg	Difference μg	Recovery %
Field water ^a	Hexane	11.0	10	20.5	9.50	95.0
		12.5	20	31.0	18.50	92.5
		21.0	40	60.0	39.00	97.5
Grapes ^b	Hexane	12.0	10	20.5	8.50	85.0
		15.0	20	34.5	19.50	97.5
		16.0	40	54.0	38.00	95.0
Cabbage ^b	Chloroform	15.0	10	24.0	9.00	90.0
		21.0	20	39.0	18.00	90.0
		25.0	40	63.5	38.50	96.25
Beans ^b	Chloroform	13.5	10	22.1	8.60	86.0
		17.0	20	36.0	19.00	96.0
		22.5	40	60.7	38.20	95.5
Blood	—	10.0	10	18.5	8.50	85.0
		11.0	20	30.7	19.20	96.0
		12.5	40	49.5	37.00	92.5

*Mean of three replicate analyses. ^aAmount of sample : 500 ml, ^bAmount of sample : 200 g.

TABLE 2—COMPARISON WITH OTHER SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHODS FOR CARBARYL

Sl. no.	Methods	λ _{max} nm	Determination range	Remarks
1.	Dimethylamino-benzaldehyde ^a	560	1.2—10	Requires 60° for colour development
2.	4-Dimethylamino-cinnamaldehyde ^a	560	0.65—6	Requires 60° for colour development
3.	<i>p</i> -Aminophenol ^b	600	0.8—10	Dye stability 7 min
4.	Dimethylphenylene diamine dihydrochloride ^b	600	0.7—8.0	Reagent toxic
5.	1-Amino-2-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid ^b	700	3.0—3.5	Reagent unstable
6.	Diazotised sulphonic acid ^c	524	2—10	Dye stability 10 min
7.	Vanillin ^d	572	2—12	Requires 60° for colour development
8.	4-Amino-phenazone ^e	475	0.5—20	Reagent unstable
9.	<i>p</i> -Aminobenzoic acid ^f	470	0.1—0.8	Dye stability 24 h, free from interference of propoxur

^aRef. 5. ^bRef. 6. ^cRef. 7. ^dRef. 8. ^eRef. 9. ^fPresent method.

sodium nitrite (0.7 ml) and 4 M NaOH (1 ml) were added and the solution was kept for 5 min when a pink dye was obtained. It was extracted with isoamyl alcohol (2 × 5 ml) and the absorbance was measured after drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate at 470 nm against a reagent blank.

Determination of carbaryl in field water : Run-off water from nearby different fields where carbaryl was spread was collected. The sample (50 ml) was extracted with hexane (50 ml) for 2—3 min. The separated aqueous layer was then extracted with hexane (2 × 25 ml). The combined hexane extracts was washed with sodium carbonate and water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and made upto 100 ml. Known aliquots of hexane were taken and hexane was evaporated off under reduced pressure on a water-bath (~50°). The residue was dissolved in ethanol (10 ml) and the colour was developed.

Determination of carbaryl in grapes : Grape samples (50 g) to which carbaryl was sprayed were meshed and carbaryl was extracted with hexane (2 × 20 ml) and determined as described above.

Determination of carbaryl in vegetables : Vegetables (cabbage, beans) samples (50 g) from different were meshed and carbaryl was extracted with chloroform (2 × 25 ml) and analysed as described earlier.

To check the validity of the method, known amounts of carbaryl was spiked to these samples and the residue obtained after evaporating n-hexane and chloroform, was analysed by the proposed method. The recoveries ranged from 85 to 97%.

Determination of carbaryl in blood of fish : Blood samples (1—2 ml) from fishes were deproteinated by trichloroacetic acid, then filtered and the filtrate was analysed for carbaryl. In order to check the validity of the method, control amounts of carbaryl was injected in these fishes. After 2 h, blood was taken out, deproteinated, filtered, and the filtrate was analysed for carbaryl as described.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Head of the Department of Chemistry, Ravishankar University, for facilities, and are thankful to Department of Bioscience for providing fish samples. One of the authors (V. A.) is thankful to R.S.U., for providing a fellowship.

References

1. W. LEITHE, "The Analysis of Air Pollutants", Ann Arbor Science Publisher, New York, 1971, p. 290.
2. C. W. STANLEY and J. S. THORNTON, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 1972, 20, 1265.
3. M. DE BEVARDMIS and W. A. WARGIN, *J Chromatogr.*, 1982, 246, 89.
4. R. W. FREI and J. F. LAWRENCE, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1972, 67, 87.
5. C. S. P. SASTRY, D. VIJAYA and K. E. RAO, *Food Chem.*, 1986, 20, 157.
6. C. S. P. SASTRY, D. VIJAYA and K. E. RAO, *Analyst*, 1987, 112, 75.
7. S. H. YUEN, *Analyst*, 1965, 90, 369.
8. S. K. HANDA and A. K. DIKSHIT, *Analyst*, 1979, 104, 1185.
9. K. M. APPAIAH, U. C. NAG, O. P. KAPUR and K. V. NAGARAJA, *J. Food Sci. Technol.*, 1983, 20, 252.